

Local Government in Germany

Responses to Urban-Rural Challenges

edited by

Martin Burgi, Lisa Hagen and Nicole Lieb

Research Center for Public Procurement Law and Administrative Cooperations
Ludwig Maximilians University of Munich

Partners

eurac
research

Eurac Research
Institute for Comparative Federalism
Italy

LMU Munich
Research Center for Public Procurement
Law and Administrative Cooperations
Germany

Autonomous University of Madrid
Institute of Local Law
Spain

Institut für Föderalismus
Institut du Fédéralisme
Institute of Federalism
University of Fribourg
Institute of Federalism
Switzerland

NALAS
Network of Associations of Local
Authorities of South East Europe
France

ximpulse GmbH
Switzerland

KDZ
Center for Public Administration Research
Austria

Council of Europe
Congress of Local and Regional Authorities
France

University of Warsaw
Institute of Political Science
Poland

ZELS
Association of the Units of Local Self-Government
North Macedonia

University of the Western Cape
Dullah Omar Institute for Constitutional
Law, Governance and Human Rights
South Africa

Addis Ababa University
Center for Federalism and Governance Studies
Ethiopia

Universidad Nacional de General San Martín
School of Politics and Government
Argentina

SALGA
South African Local Government Association
South Africa

Jawaharlal Nehru University
India

University of Technology Sydney
Institute for Public Policy and Governance
Centre for Local Government
Australia

National University of Singapore
Centre for Asian Legal Studies
Asia Pacific Centre for Environmental Law
Singapore

University of Western Ontario
Centre for Urban Policy and Local Governance
Canada

November 2021

The Country Report on Local Government in Germany is a product of the LoGov-project: “Local Government and the Changing Urban-Rural Interplay”.

The H2020-MSCA-RISE-2018 project aims to provide solutions for local governments that address the fundamental challenges resulting from urbanisation. To address these complex issues, 18 partners from 17 countries and six continents share their expertise and knowledge in the realms of public law, political science, and public administration. LoGov identifies, evaluates, compares, and shares innovative practices that cope with the impact of changing urban-rural relations in major local government areas (WP 1-5).

LICENSE

CC BY 4.0

INFORMATION

Eurac Research
Viale Druso/Drususallee, 1
39100 Bolzano/Bozen – Italy

logov@eurac.edu
www.logov-rise.eu

SCIENTIFIC COORDINATION

Eurac Research: Karl Kössler

WP 1 – Local Responsibilities and Public Services

LMU Munich: Martin Burgi

WP 2 – Local Financial Arrangements

Universidad Autónoma de Madrid: Francisco Velasco Caballero

WP 3 – Structure of Local Government

University of Fribourg: Eva Maria Belser

WP 4 – Intergovernmental Relations of Local Government

NALAS – Network of Associations of Local Authorities of South East Europe: Elton Stafa

WP 5 – People’s Participation in Local Decision-Making

Ximpulse GmbH: Erika Schläppi

EDITORIAL TEAM

LMU Munich: Martin Burgi, Lisa Hagen, Nicole Lieb
Eurac Research: Karl Kössler, Theresia Morandell, Caterina Salvo, Annika Kress, Petra Malferttheiner

GRAPHIC DESIGN

Eurac Research: Alessandra Stefanut

COVER PHOTO

Leonhard Niederwimmer/Pixabay

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 823961.

Contents

1. The System of Local Government in Germany	1
2.1. Local Responsibilities and Public Services in Germany: An Introduction	6
2.2. <i>Municipal Housing Companies</i>	8
2.3. <i>Public Health Care</i>	11
2.4. <i>Fighting Covid-19 on the Local Level</i>	17
3.1. Local Financial Arrangements in Germany: An Introduction	23
3.2. <i>Municipal Day-Care Facilities</i>	26
3.3. <i>Financing of Inter-Connected Transport Services or Linked Transportation Authorities</i>	29
3.4. <i>Public-Private Partnerships (PPP)</i>	33
4.1. The Structure of Local Government in Germany: An Introduction	40
4.2. <i>Broadband Infrastructures</i>	42
4.3. <i>Central Water Management – Water Supply and Effluent Disposal</i>	46
4.4. <i>Cooperation in the Field of Tourism</i>	51
5.1. Intergovernmental Relations of Local Governments in Germany: An Introduction	57
5.2. <i>Migration and Integration</i>	61
5.3. <i>Creation of a Further Third-Tier Administrative Unit – Munich as an Independent District</i>	65
5.4. <i>Digitalization of the Administration in Bavaria</i>	70
6.1. People’s Participation in Local Decision-Making in Germany: An Introduction	76
6.2. <i>Citizens’ Petitions for Referendum Against Essential Large-Scale Infrastructure Projects in Urban Areas</i>	79
6.3. <i>Local and Interest-Driven Parties or Independent Groups of Voters</i>	83
6.4. <i>Citizens’ Participation in Urban Planning</i>	87

Structure of Local Government

4.3. Central Water Management – Water Supply and Effluent Disposal

Lea Bosch, *Ludwig Maximilian University of Munich*

Relevance of the Practice

Water management refers to the qualitative⁹⁴ and quantitative management of water resources, i.e. water supply and effluent disposal. Water is a public good and must therefore be managed permanently and in a way that is in the best public interest. Due to various demographic changes, new challenges are emerging in water management. The change in population structures in rural and urban areas is hereby a significant factor. Demand in urban areas is increasing, while rural areas must try to keep quality standards high for a decreasing number of users. This leads in particular to prognostic uncertainties regarding future demand. In addition, the topic is currently being given special attention, as there are numerous demands for a ‘human right to water and sanitation’⁹⁵. The public water supply serves the public good.⁹⁶ The provision of drinking water as well as the disposal of sewerage is, in accordance with the division of competences laid down in the Basic Law (BL), the responsibility of the municipalities and other public bodies according to the respective *Länder*-law (see also paras 50(1), 56(1) WHG). This is a self-government task (*Selbstverwaltungsaufgabe*, i.e., a services of general interest) and thus, ultimate responsibility lies within the municipality (first sentence of Article 28(2) BL).⁹⁷

Description of the Practice

First of all, it should be noted that Germany has in general a very high drinking water quality, as tap water is drinkable (almost) everywhere. This may vary only in some regions, because of topographical reasons. The central water management including water supply and effluent disposal is carried out as public service by the municipalities. This service includes five tasks: (i) water extraction and possibly treatment of the raw water; (ii) distribution of drinking water to

⁹⁴ This task includes the protection of water resources against pollution and deterioration (particularly with regard to water quality there are strict regulations under European law), see Wolfgang Köck, ‘Zur Entwicklung des Rechts der Wasserversorgung und der Abwasserbeseitigung’ (2015) ZUR 3, 5ff.

⁹⁵ ‘The Human Right to Water and Sanitation’ (*United Nations*, 29 May 2014)

<https://www.un.org/waterforlifedecade/human_right_to_water.shtml> accessed 21 February 2020.

⁹⁶ Michael Reinhardt, ‘Demografischer Wandel im Wasserrecht – Rechtsrahmen für Daseinsvorsorge und Gewässerschutz’ (2018) LKV 289, 291.

⁹⁷ Köck, ‘Zur Entwicklung des Rechts der Wasserversorgung und der Abwasserbeseitigung’, above, 8.

final consumers (households, trade and industry, public institutions), provision of the domestic water meter; (iii) collection and discharge of waste water and rainwater; (iv) treatment of waste water and rainwater; and (v) treatment and disposal of sewage sludge.⁹⁸ As not every municipality has resources to carry out all tasks independently, different kinds of consolidations occur. The municipalities have the sovereignty to form cooperations (Article 28(2) BL), which makes it possible for different municipalities to operate jointly.

For example, in Bavaria are 2,056 municipalities and 2,350 utilities. Nevertheless, it should be noted that there is currently a tendency towards centralization, at least in terms of organizational law. Municipal mergers (permitted under the general Federal Water Association Act [*Gesetz über Wasser- und Bodenverbände, WVG*] or the respective *Länder*-laws on municipal cooperation) or cooperation in municipal supra-local companies under private law are being established (inter-municipal cooperation [*interkommunale Zusammenarbeit*], see above). Joint inter-municipal corporations (*Zweckverbände*) are set up for this purpose, which in turn transfer the organization to municipal public enterprises (government enterprises; own enterprises) or to private enterprises under private law in the hands of the municipalities (own companies).⁹⁹ The public service tasks (see above) in water management can only be transferred to private third parties under strict conditions (Section 56(1)(3) WHG).¹⁰⁰ Even in case of such a transfer, the responsibility of the municipality, in the sense of the material municipal guarantee responsibility, as well as the associated obligation to effectively perform the service, remains intact.¹⁰¹ In practice, this means that even in the event of a transfer of tasks, the municipality is responsible for monitoring. Principally, this form of performance can therefore also take place across municipal boundaries.

Moreover, public procurement law does not apply to the transfer of concessions in the domestic sphere, i.e. ultimately to the transfer of tasks to another public authority, e.g. in the context of inter-municipal cooperation.¹⁰² Interventions in the competences of other associations can only be possible as extensions of competences through inter-area economic activity by virtue of law and in compliance with the jurisdiction of the Federal Constitutional Court (*Bundesverfassungsgericht*). Moreover, some municipal laws contain opening clauses in favor of inter-territorial economic activities, which, however, always require that the interests of the foreign municipalities are safeguarded.

⁹⁸ Karin Rommel and Regina Burr, 'Wasserwirtschaftliche Daten für Stadt und Land' (2018) 9 Statistisches Monatsheft Baden-Württemberg 37 <https://www.statistik-bw.de/Service/Veroeff/Monatshefte/PDF/Beitrag18_09_08.pdf> accessed 10 March 2020>.

⁹⁹ Köck, 'Zur Entwicklung des Rechts der Wasserversorgung und der Abwasserbeseitigung', above, 8.

¹⁰⁰ For more details, see Köck, 'Zur Entwicklung des Rechts der Wasserversorgung und der Abwasserbeseitigung', above, 3.

¹⁰¹ Reinhardt, 'Demografischer Wandel im Wasserrecht', above, 292.

¹⁰² Nicole Weiß, 'Kommunale Wasserversorgung – Ungewissheit über zukünftige [ordnungspolitische] Strukturen' in Ulrich Hösch (ed), *Zeit und Ungewissheit im Recht* (Boorberg 2011) 478ff. For in-house criteria, see, among others, EuGH Rs. C-107/98 v. 18.11.1999 – Teckal; BGH, Az.: I ZR 145/05 (*Kommunalversicherer*) v. 3.7.2008.

Summarizing, municipalities have to guarantee water supply and sewage disposal as state task. There is a constitutionally warranty of equal living conditions throughout the federal territory (*Bundesgebiet*) and thus, a nationwide supply and disposal must be ensured. Municipalities can issue statutory regulations requiring residents to be connected to the water system and, in individual cases, allow for equally decentralized solutions.¹⁰³ As rural areas are experiencing a significant and worsening population decline, this – among other things – is also leading to more a difficult water management, especially regarding financial aspects. The scope of warranty of water supply and effluent disposal is only valid for those places, which already have a basic suitability for taking up residence. There is no claim to the creation of these conditions. In individual cases, turning away from a comprehensive water supply and effluent disposal system may prove to be permissible – i.e. proportionate due to economic unreasonableness for the municipality. The citizens left behind in rural areas have a high subjective interest in maintaining existing service standards.¹⁰⁴ A complete devaluation of the constitutionally protected property must of course be countervailed with compensatory measures, etc., in accordance with the requirements of the Federal Constitutional Court (*Bundesverfassungsgericht*). Decentralized, new solutions are also possible, especially in the field of effluent disposal law.¹⁰⁵ In doing so, individual planning of demand and, as a result, security of supply must be ensured due to the changing number and structure of customers. For this purpose, a smaller-scale local sewerage disposal system can be agreed upon, including decentralized effluent disposal treatment plants.

However, it remains open how this legal obligation to ensure water supply and effluent disposal will develop in consequence of the ongoing changes. The legislatures and the current legal situation therefore seem willing and able to maintain the supply of drinking water and the disposal of wastewater in rural areas. This is the only way to maintain flexibility of supply in the future.¹⁰⁶ In particular, the cooperation of many small rural local governments (RLGs) in joint inter-municipal corporations is a decisive factor in keeping the burden to be distributed in-between and as little as possible for each.

Assessment of the Practice

Proposals to strengthen competition and the possibility of privatizing water management (water supply and effluent disposal) are regularly brought up in political and legal discussions. Various demands to reform the water management law, especially for liberalization and

¹⁰³ 'However, central supply and disposal facilities clearly dominate: 99% of households in Germany are connected to the public water supply and 95% of households to sewerage and wastewater treatment facilities.', Köck, 'Zur Entwicklung des Rechts der Wasserversorgung und der Abwasserbeseitigung', above, 7f; further BMU/UBA (eds), *Wasserwirtschaft in Deutschland. Teil 1: Grundlagen* (Umweltbundesamt 2010) 86.

¹⁰⁴ Reinhardt, 'Demografischer Wandel im Wasserrecht', above, 293.

¹⁰⁵ *ibid* 294.

¹⁰⁶ *ibid* 291.

privatization, arise.¹⁰⁷ Evaluation of these proposals differs widely. In Berlin, the privatization of the utilities in 1999 resulted in such an increase in costs for the end consumer that the privatization was reversed in 2013. In general, the German model of water management is to be assessed positively: from the point of view of quality, environmental factors, and even with regard to the price-performance ratio and general cost aspects. In any case, new concepts for rural areas and their problems, especially in the technical and financial management of effluent disposal, should nevertheless be made politically and legally possible. The municipalities will not be able to implement these concepts on their own, but the existing organizational structure in joint inter-municipal corporations is beneficial. In addition to coping with demographic change and corresponding decentralization, another challenge will be dealing with climate change (increasing temperature, groundwater level, quality of water in pipes, removal of rainwater runoff). Moreover, many infrastructures are outdated and therefore in great need of renewal.

References to Scientific and Non-Scientific Publications

Legal Documents:

Report from the Commission, COM(2019) 95 final

Scientific and Non-Scientific Publications:

Burgi M, 'Privatisierung der Wasserversorgung und Abwasserbeseitigung' in Reinhard Hendler and others (eds), *Umweltschutz, Wirtschaft und kommunale Selbstverwaltung. 16. Trierer Kolloquium zum Umwelt- und Technikrecht* (Erich Schmidt Verlag 2000, 2001)

BMU/UBA (eds), *Wasserwirtschaft in Deutschland. Teil 1: Grundlagen* (Umweltbundesamt 2010)

Köck W, 'Zur Entwicklung des Rechts der Wasserversorgung und der Abwasserbeseitigung' (2015) ZUR 3

Reinhardt M, 'Demografischer Wandel im Wasserrecht – Rechtsrahmen für Daseinsvorsorge und Gewässerschutz' (2018) LKV 289

Rommel K and Burr R, 'Wasserwirtschaftliche Daten für Stadt und Land' (2018) 9 Statistisches Monatsheft Baden-Württemberg <https://www.statistik-bw.de/Service/Veroeff/Monatshefte/PDF/Beitrag18_09_08.pdf> accessed 10 March 2020>

¹⁰⁷ Martin Burgi, 'Privatisierung der Wasserversorgung und Abwasserbeseitigung' in Reinhard Hendler and others (eds), *Umweltschutz, Wirtschaft und kommunale Selbstverwaltung. 16. Trierer Kolloquium zum Umwelt- und Technikrecht* (Erich Schmidt Verlag 2000, 2001) 101ff; Weiß, 'Kommunale Wasserversorgung', above, 475ff.

Rost G and others, 'Auswirkungen eines technischen Paradigmenwechsels auf die wasserwirtschaftliche Organisation in strukturschwachen ländlichen Räumen' (2015) 73 Raumforschung, Raumordnung 343

Weiß N, 'Kommunale Wasserversorgung – Ungewissheit über zukünftige [ordnungspolitische] Strukturen' in Ulrich Hösch (ed), *Zeit und Ungewissheit im Recht* (Boorberg 2011)

Contacts

Local Government and the Changing
Urban-Rural Interplay
www.logov-rise.eu
logov@eurac.edu

This project has received funding from
the European Union's Horizon 2020 re-
search and innovation programme under
grant agreement No 823961.

